

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D2.1 – MULTI-LAYERED STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY

WP2 – Codesign

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable and its next versions will serve as a reference document among consortium partners to describe the engagement strategy of the co-design phase of project, including the methodology and approaches used for cross-disciplinary integration. The deliverable also documents the stakeholder engagement plan and its foreseen events, which is a dynamic plan for identifying and engaging all stakeholder groups.

It can also be used by policymakers and other stakeholder groups as a documentation of cross-disciplinary participatory processes and citizens' involvement.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

The DIAMOND multi-layered stakeholder engagement strategy will accompany and enrich the research process by enabling the exploration of the multiplicity of perspectives on how models can address concerns from the target groups, attending carefully to differences, complexities, and range of variation in the data.

This report provides a description of the heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology adopted in the project; illustrates the co-design process involving researchers (e.g., modellers, SSH researchers), policy makers, business, social and environmental stakeholders, and groups of citizens; and gives details on the stakeholder engagement plan.

The report also provides examples of the macro-questions to trigger each stage of the dialogue loop between researchers and practitioners aiming to co-create and assess climate change neutralization actions, and the database structure for stakeholder engagement in strategic foresight.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report. Future updates will be delivered at months 17 and 29 of the project.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
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UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

This report documents the multi-layered stakeholder engagement strategy of the DIAMOND project for model co-development, application to scenario building and policy roadmaps' co-creation exercises.

Applying a heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology, the project aspires to both equip participating models with advanced decision rules and acceptance insights on different aspects of the transition, and improve the communication, usability, uptake, and relevance of modelling results to the wider society. The integrated assessment literature has long pinpointed the benefits and challenges of opening up participation of non-expert stakeholders in modelling activities and scenario development. Wide stakeholder participation and co-production can improve the legitimacy and robustness of the modelling outputs as well as help build consensus and a sense of ownership among stakeholders over specific solutions, reinforcing the success and speed of their implementation. In order to meet this challenge and achieve understanding between diverse actors with different scientific backgrounds and traditions of thought, it is necessary to create a common frame of reference.

DIAMOND will develop continuous dialogue loops between researchers and practitioners aiming to co-create and assess climate change neutralization actions - and two boundary objects – a Three Horizons participatory foresight framework and the suite of IAMs – which will support the DIAMOND cross-disciplinary dialogue loops. Each loop iteration starts by exploring together future scenarios – *A: EXPLORE SCENARIOS* –, then goes down to test possible solutions in the modelling simulation environment – *B: SIMULATE SOLUTIONS* – to go back to assess how these solutions actually fit into present reality – *C: VALIDATE OUTCOMES* – to end with the formulation of recommended further research and policy actions – *D: FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS*. To help shaping such specific dialogues, DIAMOND identifies a list of macro-questions to trigger each stage of the dialogue loop. Six specific dialogues with researchers and stakeholders will take place within the co-design process (i.e., circular economy and climate change mitigation; land use and nature-based solutions; household heterogeneity and distributional impacts; refining climate mitigation strategies assessment; integrating finance, labour dynamics and novel operationalization of well-being; and improving the electricity system assessment). One additional ethical foresight dialogue will be organised with a representative group of citizens, focusing on behavioural change and ethical issues of climate change neutralization.

In this report, the co-design process will be developed through a path identified by three, closely connected and sequential, phases: it starts with the definition of a common knowledge base and the common understanding about the contents, objectives and limits of the DIAMOND project IAMs, it then follows with co-developing tools and knowledge and ends by jointly validating and assessing the quality of modelling improvements.

In order to meet the project expectations in terms of model co-development and policy scenarios and roadmaps co-creation, the stakeholder engagement in DIAMOND is structured through the involvement of three groups of stakeholders (i.e., the wider community of IAM developers and researchers; climate stakeholders and decision makers concerned with climate policymaking and/or climate change impacts; and citizens and civil society representatives). Ethical foresight is used to explain why the socio-political dimension needs to involve ordinary citizens to lay down the foundations for our mature information societies. The aim is to ensure a good balance of stakeholders across groups (and gender) and also maintaining stakeholder contacts throughout the project's life. The stakeholder database will be a vessel in all activities related to co-creation and engagement in WP2.

This report provides details of the foreseen events belonging to Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production: the strategic foresight workshops with stakeholders and the values and practice driven foresight with citizens.

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1 Introduction

The main purpose of the DIAMOND project is to update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes so that they provide a comprehensive and integrated framework of analysis to inform and support the design of climate policies based on:

- theories from a plurality of scientific disciplines that address causal factors and phenomena in the personal sphere (e.g. behavioural economics and psychology), in the socio-economic sphere (e.g. economics, social sciences) and in the ecological sphere (natural and life sciences)
- insights from societal actors themselves;
- empirical data from cross-national surveys of EU citizens to examine their mobility and energy use behaviours and willingness to change consumption behaviour.

Applying transdisciplinary methods, the project aspires to co-create the research questions, legitimise the implementation process and model development, and improve the communication, usability, uptake, and relevance of modelling results to the wider society.

To this end, the entire work structure of DIAMOND will be operationalised with the help of a heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology for model co-development, application to scenario building and policy roadmaps' co-creation exercises. Acknowledging that flow of knowledge spans across communities with different disciplinary and/or stakeholders' perspectives, this mechanism will ensure policy-relevant (demand-oriented) yet impartial (sound and scientifically relevant) flow of comprehensive (analytical and detailed) yet comprehensible information (for all researchers and policy makers/stakeholders involved).

To give substance to these objectives and start implementing them, here we illustrate:

- The heuristic cross-disciplinary integration methodology adopted in the project (chapter 2);
- The co-design process involving researchers (modellers), policy makers, business, social and environmental stakeholders, and groups of citizens (chapter 3);
- The detailed stakeholder engagement plan (chapter 4).

This stakeholder engagement strategy will be updated throughout the project.

2 Cross-disciplinary integration methodology

2.1 Knowledge integration: the heuristic approach to cross-disciplinary integration in DIAMOND

The integrated assessment literature has long pinpointed the benefits and challenges of opening up participation of non-expert stakeholders in modelling activities and scenario development (Van Vuuren et al., 2012; Salter et al., 2010). Wide stakeholder participation and co-production can improve the legitimacy and robustness of the modelling outputs as well as help build consensus and a sense of ownership among stakeholders over specific solutions, reinforcing the success and speed of their implementation (McGookin et al., 2021). While engagement activities with decision-makers and societal actors have been used in the past as a reality check on IAM assumptions and for assessing feasibility of their outputs, they have been rarely used to feed or further develop IAMs with a plurality of perspectives on the low-carbon transition (Braunreiter et al., 2021). Apart from availability challenges, the sheer complexity of integrated assessments and the stakeholder heterogeneity in terms of expertise, beliefs, and values can often hinder meaningful engagement in modelling, scenario development, and impact (Elsawah et al., 2020).

To go beyond this state-of-the-art, DIAMOND will continue on the path opened by previous modelling exercises that recently started employing information from stakeholders.¹ That will require the constructive combination - or *integration* - of multiple forms of expertise and perspectives, or what we shall refer to as **cross-disciplinary integration**. We use 'cross-disciplinary' as a cover term for both interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary activity. When the context requires more specificity, the term 'interdisciplinary' is used to mean the integrative combination of **disciplinary perspectives** and 'transdisciplinary' to mean the integrative combination of **disciplinary and stakeholder perspectives**.² Going across the whole range of theoretical accounts,³ they all agree that the integrative process consists in activities structured with the help of various techniques, yielding outcomes that advance cross-disciplinary research. These accounts also agree in taking integration to be *contextual*, i.e., dependent for its specific form on the context in which it is pursued, and *purposive*, i.e., a process intentionally implemented by researchers from several disciplines plus stakeholders working together in pursuit of objectives.

In the DIAMOND project, cross-disciplinarity will be understood as a "heuristic integrative research approach" that adds cooperation between academic researchers and non-academic practitioners to the inner-scientific cooperation between various disciplines, facilitating the combination of inputs into an integrated output. This knowledge integration will be more than just adding up disciplinary findings, and instead should mean the combination of heterogeneous knowledge stocks with the aim of creating an identifiable synthesis product and new insights that go beyond putting different findings side by side. To meet this challenge and achieve

¹ See for example:

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<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969721036214?via%3Dihub>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/renewable-and-sustainable-energy-transition/special-issue/10ZRPC0C1P4>
- ENGAGE
[https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frsus.2022.1063719/full?&utm_source=Email to authors &utm_medium=Email&utm_content=T1_11.5e1_author&utm_campaign=Email_publication&field=&journalName=Frontiers in Sustainability&id=1063719](https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frsus.2022.1063719/full?&utm_source=Email%20to%20authors%20&utm_medium=Email&utm_content=T1_11.5e1_author&utm_campaign=Email_publication&field=&journalName=Frontiers%20in%20Sustainability&id=1063719)

² For discussion of these modes of research, see Klein (2010).

³ See for instance O'Rourke et al. (2015)

understanding between diverse actors with different scientific backgrounds and traditions of thought, it is necessary to have a common frame of reference. In the DIAMOND project case, a common frame is provided by:

- the project objectives, and especially objective 6 (O6);⁴
- using the whole range of available IAMs, WP3 upgrades and WP4 integration modules;
- using a Three Horizons participatory foresight framework to structure participants (researchers and stakeholders) climate change neutralization scenarios building activities;
- adopting a standard dialogue loop process for seven different but coordinated foresight exercises focused on:
 1. *Circular economy and climate change mitigation* (jointly with Task 4.1: An integrated framework for circular economy & mitigation).
 2. *Land use and nature-based solutions* (jointly with Task 4.2: Improving the representation of land use, nature-based solutions).
 3. *Household heterogeneity and distributional impacts* (jointly with Task 4.3: Distributional impacts: refining household heterogeneity).
 4. *Refining climate mitigation strategies assessment* (jointly with Task 4.4: Linking IAMs to climate/physical impact models).
 5. *Integrating finance, labour dynamics and novel operationalization of well-being* (jointly with Task 4.5: Integrating finance, labour dynamics, and well-being in IAMs).
 6. *Improving the electricity system assessment* (jointly with Task 4.7: A finer detail of electricity in IAMs for interconnectivity in EU).
 7. In addition, one ethical foresight dialogue will be organised with a representative group of citizens, focusing on *behavioural change and ethical issues of climate change neutralization*, also taking stock of Task 4.6: Representation of behavioural aspects & preferences for action results and of Task 4.3 analysis of household heterogeneity.

Figure 1 shows the DIAMOND dialogue loops between researchers and practitioners aiming to co-create and assess climate change neutralization actions, with the support of two “boundary objects”⁵: a Three Horizons participatory foresight framework and the suite of IAMs, WP3 upgrades and WP4 integration modules. As stated in the PARIS REINFORCE Policy Briefs⁶, models cannot be expected to produce fundamentally “true” policy insights,

⁴ To develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to co-create the research questions, legitimize the implementation process and model development, and optimize the communication of project results, with representatives from policy, business, and civil society, allowing to translate the motives, concerns, and actions of decision-makers and citizens over climate action in measurable, quantifiable terms and to demonstrate how they can affect and contribute to the wider climate policy and sustainable development objectives.

⁵ Broadly speaking, in the field of cross-disciplinary research such diverse objects as scenarios (e.g., scenarios for the deployment of renewable energy), models (e.g., climate models), interdisciplinary frameworks and concepts (e.g., ecosystem services framework or biodiversity), spatial foci (e.g., case studies in a specific city or region), among others, are considered and applied as boundary objects. a boundary object works well if it establishes a shared language so that the different cooperating actors can represent their knowledge, enabling them to learn about their differences and dependencies (e.g., on undisclosed stereotypes) and facilitating a common process of knowledge transformation and integration.

⁶ PARIS REINFORCE Policy Briefs: <https://paris-reinforce.eu/publications/policy-briefs>.

but to feed **constructive dialogues** regarding inputs into the model, as well as the interpretation of results.

Figure 1. DIAMOND common cross-disciplinary goal

Source: Own elaboration

Now, the ambition of DIAMOND is to develop such constructive dialogues to co-create and assess climate change neutralization policies and actions, and these should become an activity that, framed and started to co-design IAMs applications and scenarios during the project life (WP2 – Co-design) will continue beyond the project life, as a permanent DIAMOND open community task (WP6 – Open). This is represented in **Figure 1** above by a loop connecting stakeholders/practitioners' real-life perspectives and the scientific evidence perspective embedded in the modelling structure and reality simulation functions, to co-produce a mutual understanding of the complex climate change challenge and devise possible responses. Each loop iteration starts by exploring together future scenarios – A: *EXPLORE SCENARIOS* –, then goes down to test possible solutions in the modelling simulation environment – B: *SIMULATE SOLUTIONS* – to go back to assess how these solutions actually fit into present reality – C: *VALIDATE OUTCOMES* – to end with the formulation of recommended further research and policy actions – D: *FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS*.

It is important to note that:

- i. After a first policy co-creation iteration that will be tested within the DIAMOND lifetime, the same heuristic approach of knowledge integration should be used to replicate integrated assessment exercises, continuing to involve both researchers and stakeholders, as a form of project exploitation activity.
- ii. The whole DIAMOND project scope is too wide to develop a meaningful dialogue covering all the climate change neutralization related issues simultaneously in one process. It is more feasible and meaningful to develop constructive dialogues – using the same format – for the specific extensions (WP4 – Integrate & Expand) and user-driven scenario exploration tasks in WP5 – Apply & Explore (Task 5.4: Stretching the frontiers – user-driven scenarios and Task 5.5: Expanding the SDG target space) planned in the project.

To help shaping such specific dialogues, **Table 1** (also in **Table 4** in Annex I) lists “stem questions”⁷ that will be further specified depending on the specific dialogues contexts, to trigger each stage of the dialogue loop:

Table 1. “Stem questions” of the dialogue loop

Stage A - EXPLORE SCENARIOS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why we need to take climate change neutralization decisions now (challenging trends)? • What if scenarios (game changers, shocks)?
Stage B – SIMULATE SOLUTIONS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What should be done to reduce global warming and adapt to climate change? (co-design of assumptions) • What model simulations can tell us? (interpretation of results)
Stage C: VALIDATE SIMULATION OUTCOMES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the suggested solutions fit back into present reality? If yes, how? If not, why not?
Stage D. FORMULATE RESEARCH & POLICY AGENDAS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which further research and policy actions to do in practice?

The columns of **Table 4** in Annex I will show when filled with information during stakeholder engagement, for each of the above stem-questions, the specific research questions identified from the scientific side (by DIAMOND partners) in the first column, from the user side (invited stakeholders’ representatives) in the second column, and the shared questions consolidated by matching the two perspectives, which will be co-created to trigger/guide each specific online dialogue.

A table of specific research questions will be compiled dynamically for each of the seven dialogues, producing a draft version before each dialogue step (workshop) to show examples of relevant questions identified in the preparation stage (as a result of interviews or desk research) and a final version after, updated with the research questions co-created as dialogue outcomes.

2.2 Three horizons foresight framework

Through the lens of a multi-layer stakeholder analysis, the DIAMOND project will engage invited representatives of four main target layers of actors – policy makers, business and social stakeholders, environmental stakeholders and citizens – together with researchers (DIAMOND modelling teams) in a cross-disciplinary process of user-driven climate change neutralization scenarios exploration, interpretation and impact assessment. This activity will apply the Three Horizons participatory foresight framework. This is a tool that helps to structure the thinking about the future of a multi-disciplinary & multi-stakeholders’ group in ways that spark innovation. It describes three patterns or ways of doing things and how their relative prevalence and interactions evolve over time. The change from the

⁷ In biology, stem cells are the body's raw materials — cells from which all other cells with specialized functions are generated. Here we use the notion of “stem questions” with the same meaning, i.e. general questions that will generate specialized questions in the different DIAMOND dialogue contexts (the seven thematic dialogues mentioned earlier).

established pattern of the first horizon to the emergence of fundamentally new patterns in the third occurs via the transition activity of the second horizon. The model not only makes us think in interactive patterns, but more importantly it draws attention to the three horizons always existing in the present moment, and that we have evidence about the future in how people (including ourselves) are behaving now. As told by the main author, "the essence of Three Horizons practice is to develop both an individual and a shared awareness of all three horizons, seeing them as perspectives that must all come into the discussion, and to work flexibly with the contributions that each one makes to the continuing process of renewal on which we all depend. We step out of our individual mindset into a shared space of creative possibility." (Sharpe, 2013).

Horizon 1 is 'business as usual', or 'the world in crisis' (H1). It is characterized by 'sustaining innovation' that keeps 'business as usual' going. Horizon 3 is how we envision a 'viable world' (H3). We may not be able to define this future in every detail – as the future is always uncertain – yet we can intuit what fundamental transformations lie ahead, and we can pay attention to social, ecological, economic, cultural, and technological experiments around us that may be pockets of this future in the present. Horizon 2 represents 'world in transition' (H2) – the entrepreneurial and culturally creative space of already technologically, economically, and culturally feasible innovations that can disrupt and transform H1 to varying degrees and can have either regenerative, neutral or degenerative socio-ecological effects.

At the point where these H2 innovations become more effective than the existing practices, they begin to replace aspects of 'business as usual'. Yet some forms of disruptive innovation ultimately get absorbed by H1 without leading to fundamental and transformative change, while other forms of disruptive innovation can be thought of as a possible bridge from H1 to H3. It is useful therefore to classify H2 innovations into two categories. The first category is called H2- (Horizon 2 minus). H2- innovations change the technology employed and therefore disrupt 'business as usual' temporarily but without leading to a profound systemic transformation. The second category is H2+ (Horizon 2 plus). H2+ innovations offer a bridge to H3, leading to a structural change and transformation of the system in question. For example, providing power to the national grid via large-scale windfarms is on the one hand part of the H2+ strategy of moving towards a 100% renewable energy-based system, and on the other hand an H2- innovation locked into an H1 mindset as it is still structurally supporting a centralized energy system. An example of a genuine H2+ innovation in this area would be a blend of diverse and decentralized renewable energy technologies that combine stand-alone and grid-connected options to increase the flexibility, efficiency, and resilience of the energy system overall.

The Three Horizons framework (**Figure 2**) will be used in the DIAMOND dialogue loops to discuss two typologies of scenarios: more conservative (H1) climate policy scenarios, mostly envisaging the deployment of the currently dominant technological trends and climate mitigation and adaptation policies; and the more transformative (H3) scenarios, which consider not only the impact of new technological and economic measures, but also possible behavioural, social and cultural changes switching towards a regenerative economy paradigm (see box below). Both categories of scenarios will diverge from the "do nothing" scenario (i.e., that taken as reference, where there are no policy measures or other changes influencing the business as usual trends – we call it H0), but with a different intensity and sustainability outcome (see box below).

Figure 2. 3H methodology applied to envision conservative vs transformative climate change neutralization scenarios (Participatory Foresight Framework)

Source: Own elaboration

Figure 3. Switching to a regenerative economy using 3H

Source: Adapted from J. Fullerton (2015), *Regenerative Capitalism*, Capital Institute, p. 43

The rationale of switching to a regenerative economy paradigm worldwide is increasingly evident. We are in a situation where rapid change to a healthy relationship with the planet is in order. In this respect, the concept of “regeneration” and “regenerative growth” moves our frame of discourse from “doing things to nature” to “participate as partners with and as nature”. At the core of the regeneration paradigm there is conceiving the economic system literally as a living system, working with the same universal pattern of self-organization, interdependence between and diversity of the various parts connected in a whole organic system. By taking this regenerative worldview we radically change the concept of sustainability. Rather than a “goal” measured

by targets that can be achieved and then maintained forever after, sustainability is interpreted as a dynamic “process” of nature and human techno-sphere co-evolution, and a community-based process of continuous conversation and learning how to participate appropriately in the constantly transforming life-sustaining processes that we are part of and that our future depends upon. What a regenerative economy would sustain is the underlying pattern of planetary and human health, resilience and adaptability that maintain this planet in a condition where life satisfaction and human well-being can flourish.

The best-known example of regenerative economy is in the agriculture sector, where it is now technologically possible and economically competitive to produce food while simultaneously living the plot of land better off, but regeneration can work across all development sectors – not just agriculture – going beyond sustainability. The question in sustainable development was “*How can the economy work in such a way that we sustain or do not hurt the underlying (ecological and social) support systems?*” Now, the question in regenerative development becomes “*How can the economy work in such a way that we improve the capacity of the underlying support systems?*”. It is no more enough do not harm, sustainability and zero-waste and zero-emissions policies are noble goals, but we can and must do better than zero, we need to do good – this is the key message of regenerative economy.

Given the wide ‘diversity’ of the stakeholders’ categories involved in the cross-disciplinary process, a detailed evaluation of each stakeholder’s motivations and expectations is relevant, and for creating a mutual understanding it will be beneficial to match in the DIAMOND dialogue loops the scientific knowledge embodied in the IAM models with the values, mind-sets and experiential perspectives of users/stakeholders, by enabling a two-way communication and discussion of the rationale (i.e. assumptions) and of the results (i.e. the interpretation) of modelling simulations.

This “matching” is achieved by immersing the holders of different kinds of knowledge – scientific and experiential – in the dialogue setting represented as **synergic sense making space** in **Figure 4** below. This conceptual representation of the DIAMOND dialogue setting considers:

- Three definitions of the term “sense” to identify a 3D field of synergic sense making from three angles: 1) sense as meaning (the scientific knowledge perspective), 2) sense as sensation/feeling (the practitioners knowledge perspective), and 3) sense as way to/direction (the forward-looking systemic perspective shared by both scientists and practitioners).
- Four fields of simultaneously co-existing systemic relations between agents – represented in the figure as superimposed layers, but tightly interwoven in reality: the ecological, economy & technology, society & culture, and political layers.
- A purpose-driven dialogue process generated by using the Three Horizon framework and combining dialogue loops focused on the transitions towards transformative scenarios in the different layers.
- The synergic sense making game players, i.e. the participants involved in the dialogue loops from the different practical perspectives - policy makers, environmental stakeholders, business & social stakeholders, citizens – and from nested holistic evidence-based perspectives. The latter are “holistic” insofar as they combine multiple disciplines to explain human behaviour (“ego-logy”), the economy and innovation dynamics (“eco-nomy”), the ecosystem dynamics (“eco-logy”) and finally the influence of historical, societal and cultural value contexts (“context-ology”, the focus of social science, art and humanities). It is useful to note that “ego-logy”, “eco-

“Eco-nomy” and “eco-ecology” are nested holistic perspectives, i.e. holons⁸, while “context-ology” is key to contextualise any intervention – policy, decision, investment, etc. – in the real-life setting.

Figure 4. The Diamond participatory foresight space
 Source: Own elaboration

In this space – an immaterial boundary object - researchers (modellers) and different groups of stakeholders will meet and confront themselves from different perspectives. The scientific evidence-informed modelling of individual/household behaviour, economy, natural processes, and policy regulations will have to be married with the value-driven mindsets and experiential knowing of lay citizens, business & social stakeholders, environmental stakeholders, and policy makers, to discuss relevant topics in the different macro-layers: ecological, economy and technology, society and culture, political.

Relevant topics may include mostly drivers and/or measures affecting, e.g., the people behaviour in the society & culture layer, productivity gains achievement and distribution in the economic layer (or total wealth creation if we expand productivity to include economic, natural, and social impact), emissions and climate impacts in the ecological, and policy regulations in the political layer. In this process, conversations “across the boundaries” will

⁸ A holon (Greek: ὅλον, from ὅλος, holos, 'whole' and -ον, -on, 'part') is something that is simultaneously a whole in and of itself, as well as a part of a larger whole. In other words, holons can be understood as the constituent part-wholes of a hierarchy. “Ego-logy”, looking to individuals, “Eco-nomy” looking to economic systems, and “Eco-ecology” looking to ecological systems are in an holonic hierarchy. In other terms, holistic thinking considers the individual immersed in nested systems of relations internally with himself (body and mind organisms and functions), and externally in economic (market and non-market) and ecological relations. These systems of relations exist and evolves in concrete geographical, historical, anthropological, and cultural contexts, which is what human sciences study most (“context-ology”), and eventually influence most of the policy makers decisions.

help participants to disclose the ingrained disciplinary or mind frames, filtering their own vision of the reality of such things as, for instance, what is driving the adoption of a certain innovation. Modellers could discover hidden motivations and drivers, that could be feasible to include in a model to build more realistic representations, while stakeholders could overcome mental barriers against innovation by better understanding potential benefits or how to handle trade-offs. This whole process of ‘collective intelligence’ will be catalysed by sharing the third dimension shown in the cross-disciplinary space graphic, i.e., the imagination of the future impact of climate change neutralization measures and how they would contribute to accelerate the transition towards climate change neutralization scenarios.

2.3 DIAMOND integrated assessment modelling framework

The first boundary object was a purely abstract think – the Three Horizons scheme applied to frame transition scenarios. The second boundary object is still immaterial, but more concrete, being a collection of Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) codified with software procedures and databases. While the first object has by definition the highest interpretive flexibility – it is a shared language for collaborative future thinking that can be adapted to the purpose and context of specific foresight exercises to deliver scenario narratives and policy roadmaps – the second object it is unavoidably more rigid.

This is because models are a code environment that provides a structured testing ground to simulate the effects of hypothetical assumptions, and they can be modified to a certain extent, but never without efforts. Moreover, models are a broad approximation to reality: they are only good as the assumptions fed into them, but there will be always relevant aspects that escape quantification and can only be considered in a qualitative fashion in the scenario narratives. Often these qualitative aspects are equally important as simulated outcomes, and they can be fundamental to interpret some quantitative results. This is also the reason why in DIAMOND we suggest to combine the two boundary objects – the participatory foresight framework and the IAMs – together to feed forward-looking dialogue loops.

The following is the list of the models used in DIAMOND is summarised in **Table 2**. For more information on the models, see project deliverable “D3.1 Model development strategy” and the I²AM PARIS platform.⁹

Table 2. Models used in DIAMOND

NEMESIS
NEMESIS is a sectoral detailed macro-econometric model for the EU used to assess a wide spectrum of policies, including fiscal, budgetary, labour market, research and innovation, energy, climate, and environment.
OMNIA
TIAM is a leading partial-equilibrium, inter-temporal optimisation IAM, based on the TIMES model generator, along with which it has been used to support national and international climate policy. DIAMOND will produce OMNIA, featuring fully open access.
PROMETHEUS
PROMETHEUS is a global energy system model covering in detail the complex interactions between energy demand, supply and energy prices at the regional and global level.

⁹ <https://www.i2am-paris.eu/>

GCAM

GCAM is a dynamic-recursive model with technology-rich representations of the economy, energy sector, land use and water linked to a climate model that can be used to explore climate change mitigation policies.

CLEWs

CLEWs is a nexus modelling framework for integrated assessment of resource systems and of interlinkages among energy, water, and agricultural systems as well as their impacts on—and vulnerability to—climate change.

GEMINI-E3

GEMINI-E3 is a multi-country, multi-sector, recursive computable general equilibrium (CGE) model. It simulates all relevant markets, domestic and international.

3 The Co-design process

The co-design process elaborates on the stakeholder engagement, which, is structured through the involvement of researchers (modellers), policy makers, business, social and environmental stakeholders, and groups of citizens, to achieve model co-development and co-creation of policy scenarios and roadmaps.

3.1 The DIAMOND approach and objectives

DIAMOND will conduct an open and cross-disciplinary research process based on adjusting and integrating knowledge from the wider IAM community and relevant experts from other scientific disciplines (e.g., psychology, behavioural economics, labour economics), as well as from policy, industry, and civil society stakeholders. This process will accompany and enrich all other methodological modules of the project: it will refine the requirements for model improvements (UPDATE & UPGRADE), pinpoint critical aspects for climate action that are currently missing from (or underrepresented in) IAMs (INTEGRATE & EXPAND), jointly co-create currently unexplored mitigation scenarios to simulate using the improved models (APPLY & EXPLORE), and codesign communication tools and applications of IAM results that are useful and user-friendly (OPEN). Most co-productive activities will take stock of experience/knowledge systematised in the td-net toolbox¹⁰ of transdisciplinary methods, allowing us to create a community of experts and societal actors that will inform project activities based on a distributed model of knowledge instead of a hierarchical one. This cross-disciplinary process will help us explore the multiplicity of perspectives on IAMs, understand how new models and scenarios address concerns from diverse stakeholders as well as map actionable knowledge and ensure usability via participatory development and validation.

Basing on this general and conceptual framework at the end of its implementation, path the DIAMOND co-design process will provide the following key outcomes:

- Co-produce the guiding questions to ensure transformational impact of our modelling framework in practice.
- Implement an interactive, cross-disciplinary approach to inform modelling improvements and ensuing scenarios.
- Validate all project outputs to ensure policy relevance, usefulness in industry, and societal robustness.

3.2 Which types of stakeholders to be involved

As already outlined in the previous chapter, to implement in the most effective manner the DIAMOND cross-disciplinary co-design process, the project will involve three groups of stakeholders as shown in **Figure 5** below:

¹⁰ The [td-net toolbox](#) is an online resource platform containing different methods for systematically co-producing knowledge in heterogenous groups across science and society.

Figure 5. Types of stakeholders in DIAMOND

Source: Own elaboration

In the first group, we will engage with the wider community of IAM developers and researchers to involve them in the development of the new, enhanced, open-source IAMs as well as relevant datasets and applications. Key experts to invite will include the coordinators of other European or national research IAM-oriented projects in support of climate, energy, and environmental/sustainability policies (e.g., WorldTrans, PRISMA, LOCOMOTION, NAVIGATE). To guarantee a robust interdisciplinary integration process, representatives from SSH disciplines will actively participate in the analysis of societal impacts related to climate policies.

In the second group, we will invite climate stakeholders and decision makers concerned with climate policymaking and/or climate change impacts to understand their perspectives, expectations, and requirements. This broad group encompasses several categories, including but not limited to EC and national policymakers (including negotiators in UNFCCC processes), local governments, industry, business associations, NGOs, unions, and other institutions.

In the third group, we will invite citizens and civil society representatives concerned with future impacts of climate change and climate-related actions on everyday life and the ethical acceptability of policy measures to further inform model development and increase societal relevance.

The actor constellation¹¹ method will be used to identify the stakeholders that could contribute to and benefit from the project using, acknowledging the increasing complexity of global, multi-level environmental governance (Jänicke, 2008; Feldoff, Fanderl, Stockmann, Gahle, 2019).

3.3 The Co-design pathway

3.3.1 Multi-stakeholder co-design process

The co-design process will develop through a path identified by three, closely connected and sequential, phases: it starts with the definition of a common knowledge base and the common understanding about the contents, objectives and limits of the DIAMOND project IAMs, it then follows with co-developing tools and knowledge and ends by jointly validating and assessing the quality of modelling improvements.

Phase 1 – Towards mutual understanding and framing of project goals and requirements.

In the first phase of the project, we will explore how IAMs are being perceived by different stakeholders and identify relevant understandings on current IAM gaps and needs. We will use the “but why” technique (Virapongse et al., 2020) to extensively discuss the existing situation and reach to the root causes of problems with current IAMs as well as define research questions from the perspective of different fields of knowledge (project partners) and practice (stakeholders). Moreover, we will employ multi-stakeholder discussion groups (Fry, 2021) to ensure that our project asks relevant research questions from the point of view of societal priorities and stakeholder interests and will complement this qualitative approach with representative studies to examine how IAM outputs are understood and interpreted by the public. Based on this multimethodological assessment, we will identify the respective demand for knowledge that the improved IAMs will need to provide. In this context, we will also identify citizen-sensitive research topics—i.e., related to behavioural change and societal transformation practices at small scale, but with the potential to deliver effective impacts if upscaled (Nikas et al., 2020). More details on the description of this phase will be provided in deliverable “D2.2-Stakeholder-informed research questions”.

The main aim of this phase is reaching a mutual understanding of models’ interpretations and needs. The output will take the form of research questions from the perspectives of researchers and stakeholders, respectively, and of shared co-created research questions that will be used in the next phase 2 of knowledge co-production to trigger the DIAMOND dialogue loops illustrated in section 2.2.1, filling the template included in Annex I of this deliverable with questions identified for the six specific dialogue loops (related to the WP4 extensions).

Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production

This is the main phase of the stakeholder engagement process, aiming to involve the different groups of stakeholders either in co-developing the IAMs tools upgrades and in co-producing scenarios making use of the expanded tools. Along with members from the broader IAM community (in collaboration with H2020 ECEMF and the IAMC, openmod, OpTIMUS, CCG, IEA-ETSAP, IEW, EMP-E, and CLEWs communities/networks), we will organise capacity building activities to co-develop new modelling capabilities and harmonise modelling assumptions/inputs in order to address across-the-board gaps and needs of the community. The use of these improvements will not be restricted to the DIAMOND modelling armoury but will be made available to duplicate in/export to other IAMs and accompanied with adequate support and training material. In parallel, we will engage

¹¹ According to the Swiss Academy of Sciences (SCNAT), an actor constellation is a role-play, in which all scientific and societal actors involved in a project are represented and positioned around the central research question. The distance from an actor to the research question, and to other actors, expresses how relevant (s)he is in the project.

with the group of stakeholders and decision makers in scenario planning workshops to envision and assess alternative, feasible, and desirable policy scenarios. We will reflect on validity problems associated with existing reference/baseline scenarios to which modelling research anchors and subsequently improve these scenarios by accounting for current policies, restrictions, and game-changing issues. Thus, we will first understand what “we are currently looking at” before grasping “what we need to do against that”. For this, we will employ a “strategic foresight” methodology (Iden et al., 2017), a systematic approach for stakeholders to look beyond current expectations, account for a variety of plausible future developments, and identify implications for policies. More in detail, we will apply here the heuristic approach to cross-disciplinary integration described in section 2.2 to frame six dialogue loops focused on the DIAMOND WP4 planned extensions. In addition, an “ethical foresight” approach (Floridi and Strait, 2020) will be used to engage with our citizens group, looking into the ethical implications of technology development and policies, focusing on what is actually feasible in everyday practice, and privileging—within this—what is environmentally sustainable, socially acceptable, and preferable by the citizens (see section 3.3.2.1 below). This will be complemented by representative surveys allowing to make assumptions about the support of various policies and scenarios in the public as well as associated risk perceptions. Through this approach, we will define reference scenarios and modelling improvements for IAMs that respond to the most relevant citizens’ concerns, perceptions, needs, and desires. As described in section 3.3.2.2 below, climate-friendly practice workshops with citizens will be organised to develop scenarios for a sustainable transition based on local practices and behavioural shifts that could be transformed into powerful, bottom-up actions for climate mitigation and adaptation, drawing from recent experience of consortium partners in H2020 projects (e.g., Nikas et al., 2021).

Finally, the outputs of the strategic (with the stakeholders) and ethical (with the citizens) foresight exercises will be synthesised using a Situation Analysis (Task 2.3.3). This qualitative interpretative method will explore the multiplicity of perspectives as they will emerge in the dialogue loops structured with the heuristic cross-disciplinary integration approach described in section 2.2 above.

Phase 3 – Towards model co-ownership

In the last phase, all stakeholder groups will be brought together to jointly validate and assess the quality of modelling improvements and ensuing scenarios with respect to scientific credibility and contribution to the IAM community (researchers), practical relevance (decision makers, industries, and NGOs), and societal robustness (civil society). We will use the emancipatory boundary critique (Pohl, 2020) to uncover priorities and assumptions of the different stakeholders within project outputs—for instance, system boundaries that were set when creating the new IAMs and aspects that were stressed or neglected in defining scenarios. Most importantly, we will employ the “most significant change” method (Wülser, 2020) to evaluate the impact of implemented model improvements and scenarios and discuss them considering stakeholders’ interests. Finally, we will identify potential impacts that the project can achieve in the mid- and longer term.

Figure 6. The co-design pathway in DIAMOND

Source: Own elaboration

3.3.2 Citizens' involvement

3.3.2.1 Why do we need to involve citizens?

In the process of building a mature information and sustainable society, the real challenge is not only building technological innovation but also governance of social and ethical impacts. **Ethical foresight** is crucial to explain why the socio-political dimension needs to involve ordinary citizens to lay down the foundations for our mature

information and sustainable societies.

When policymakers, both in political and in business contexts, wonder why we should engage in moral evaluation when legal compliance is already available, the answer should be clear: compliance is necessary but insufficient to steer society in the right direction. Ethical problems matter and we must engage with stakeholders affected by such ethical problems. Because regulation indicates what the legal and illegal moves in the game are, but it says nothing about what the good and best moves could be to have a better society (EDPS Ethics Advisory Group, 2018). So, the task of ethical foresight is not simply to forecast the most plausible future developments, but also to determine which ones should grow and which should not. In other words, we need to anticipate and steer the ethical development of technological innovation. And we can do this by looking at what is actually feasible, privileging, within this, what is environmentally sustainable, then what is socially acceptable and then, ideally, choose what is socially preferable (Floridi, 2018).

3.3.2.2 Climate-friendly practice workshops

Citizens and civil society representatives concerned with future impacts of climate change and climate-related actions on everyday life and the ethical acceptability of policy measures will be involved with DIAMOND through climate-friendly practice workshops, taking inspiration from the transition practice workshops held in the ENABLE.EU Horizon 2020 project ([link](#)). The DIAMOND Climate-friendly Practice Workshop aims to elicit the opinions of 40 citizens to further inform model development and increase societal relevance. The results of the workshop will also feed the exploitation plan with possible replication opportunities of the DIAMOND approach into other projects.

4 Stakeholder engagement plan

4.1 Organisation of stakeholders mapping and database

ISINNOVA will organize the process of managing and completing the initial database of stakeholders to be involved by Month 6. The structure of the database will follow the structure shown in **Table 5** in Annex II). The database will be filled in with relevant stakeholder contacts of each project partner. The aim is to ensure a good balance of stakeholders across groups (and gender) and also maintaining stakeholder contacts throughout the project's life. The stakeholder database will be a vessel in all activities related to cocreation and engagement in WP2.

The mapping of the stakeholders will be done following the 6 aforementioned specific dialogues:

1. Circular economy and climate change mitigation
2. Land use and nature-based solutions
3. Household heterogeneity and distributional impacts
4. Refining climate mitigation strategies assessment
5. Integrating finance, labour dynamics and novel operationalization of well-being
6. Improving the electricity system assessment

An additional category "Other cross-cutting interest" is added to include all the stakeholders not classified or classifiable under the other categories who have more general interests regarding climate change.

Each dialogue will count on the participation of the following categories, who have been initially identified and will be further refined during the project (Tasks 2.1 & 7.2):

- **Modellers from the DIAMOND team** working on integrated assessment modelling and scenario analysis who can adopt the project's open-source improvements in their own models.
- **Researchers** (e.g., modellers outside the consortium and non-modeller researchers) working on climate change mitigation who can inform their work through the project outcomes.
- **Climate stakeholders:**
 - **Policymakers** at different levels (e.g., national authorities, EC DGs, UNFCCC negotiators).
 - Representatives from **Industries** of different sectors who can exploit results to take more robust decisions in issues related to mitigation and adaptation, considering important but previously unexplored issues such as impacts from extreme events and the implications of circularity strategies.
- **Civil society organisations, NGOs and citizens in general** who will be provided with insights on how small-scale actions and lifestyle changes can contribute to broad climate targets and what the benefits and burdens of these actions are.

4.2 Planning of the stakeholders engagements events

4.2.1 Phase 1 – Towards mutual understanding and framing of project goals and requirements

The detailed description of this phase will be provided in deliverable “D2.2-Stakeholder-informed research questions”.

4.2.2 Phase 2 – Towards knowledge co-production

This phase aims to involve the different groups of stakeholders either in co-developing the IAM upgrades and in co-producing alternative, feasible, and desirable policy scenarios that respond to the most relevant citizens’ concerns, perceptions, needs, and desires.

4.2.2.1 Strategic foresight workshops with stakeholders (Task 2.3.1)

Three main workshops are going to be held, all organised via online conference platforms with a MURAL board supporting the interaction and lasting approximately 3 hours:

- Requirements Workshop: co-define the requirements of IAM improvements in order to best respond to relevant stakeholders’ concerns.
- Reference Scenarios Workshop: validate realistic reference scenarios describing where we are heading based on current policies.
- Alternative Scenarios Workshop: envision and assess alternative/desirable policy scenarios.

The workshops, although different in scope, will follow the Three Horizons framework and will be planned and managed in a similar way in order to ensure maximum efficiency and consistency of results. For each event, ISINNOVA will:

- Ensure a transparent and inclusive participation process and timely invitation.
- Prepare and sent background documents to the participants before each workshop. A brief will be shared containing information regarding the project, aims and progress as well as the Agenda and the objectives of the related workshop.
- Apply the facilitation techniques most suitable for the workshop aims and participants.
- Draft workshop reports to be then analysed to gathered insights for the next stages.

The workflow will be articulated in three consecutive steps as follows: preparatory step phase, workshops step and reporting step:

1. **Preparatory step**, focused on three main activities:
 - Workshop organisation – selecting dates, streamlining the invitation process and defining workshops roles.
 - Workshop brief – prioritizing what to present in order to make it easily understandable to the workshop participants thus allowing swift and effective interaction during the workshop sessions.
 - Workshop operational design – selection of facilitation techniques and supporting tools, preparation of agenda, workshop guide and report template.
2. **Workshops step**. The three specialised workshops will follow a similar structure in which:

- In the first session, the team shortly recaps the project objectives and methods.
- In the second session interactive breakout rooms will be moderated by a member of the team to gather inputs from the participants.
- A plenary will be held to compare and summarize the group’s discussion findings

For each workshop, the following roles will be distributed among the DIAMOND team members:

- Moderator and rapporteur:
 - Remind participants of the task and encourage the discussion to begin.
 - Try to keep the discussion on topic by bringing it back if it starts to drift. Prompts are provided for each activity
 - Ensure all participants have a chance to contribute to the discussion: encourage non-contributing participants to engage
 - Double-check that breakout room has been recording
 - Capture the key points of the discussion
 - Synthesise all different perspectives
 - Share the highlights of the discussion during the plenary session in no more than 5 minutes
- Discussant:
 - Have the technical role of co-host to share slides
 - Present the project in no more than 15 minutes
 - Try to be as receptive as possible to participants ideas and sensitivities
 - Intervene in the discussion when explicitly requested by participants and moderator
- Note taker:
 - Have the technical role of co-host to record breakout rooms
 - Click on recording when the breakout room is open
 - Capture the discussion by taking as much notes as possible

3. **Reporting step.** To summarize the results of the workshops results and feed them to the next stages of the project in order to influence tool development and drive applications that are customised to the needs and abilities of each stakeholder group.

Table 3. Structure for the organisation of strategic foresight workshops

WHAT	HOW			WHEN	WHO
	Mode	Methodology	Frame		
Requirements	Online	3H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breakout rooms ● MURAL support 	Month 23	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team facilitators ● Stakeholders
Reference Scenarios	Online	3H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breakout rooms ● MURAL support 	Month 24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team facilitators ● Stakeholders
Alternative Scenarios	Online	3H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Breakout rooms ● MURAL support 	Month 25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team facilitators ● Stakeholders

4.2.2.2 Values and practice driven foresight with citizens (Task 2.3.2)

Ethical foresight activities aim to elicit a better understanding of people values, beliefs and habits that drive everyday consumption practice and investment (durable goods and services) choices, reflect on how these contribute at an aggregate level to global warming and climate change, with the help of IAM-based analyses.

Details on how to organise in practice such ethical foresight dialogue loops will be described in the next issue of D2.1 (Month 17), also based on the results of Tasks 4.3 and 4.6, which will respectively clarify to what extent and how the heterogeneity of households' behaviour and behavioural change for desirability of climate action is represented in the IAMs, and so which kind of answers these models can provide to questions on the matter.

However, what can be anticipated here is the general approach that we plan to follow to engage the citizens. This will be done considering some principles:

- **Concrete choices and impacts:** citizens, divided in focus groups, will be asked to consider their concrete habits, behaviours and choices in the real everyday life practice concerning:
 - Energy at home
 - Mobility
 - Food
 - Waste
- **People-relevant research questions:** A first question will aim to raise people awareness of the more global consequences of their own individual behaviours and choices, that emerge when data are aggregated in model computations and scenarios. Other questions will follow that apply a sort of subsidiarity principle, asking what can be done first by people/households themselves, what by people aggregated in communities of collective consumption or production, and then what should be done by governments, at different levels (local, regional, national, global). The following are examples of such questions:
 - To what extent and how people choices have an impact on climate change?
 - What can we do by changing our individual/household behaviour and/or investment choices to mitigate/adapt to climate change?
 - What can be done at community level, by changing collective behaviour?
 - What the governments can/should do to help people changing behaviours towards climate-neutral everyday life and investment in durable goods/services choices?
 - To what extent and how this will contribute to change people well-being?
- **Citizens' engagement strategy:** an efficient and potentially more effective approach will be to select and recruit the target of 40 citizens from those responding to the online citizens survey organised in Task 4.6 to investigate behavioural changes for climate-neutral action. Survey responses can be scanned to identify groups of citizens with different personal profile (age, gender, other relevant characteristics asked in the survey) and typology of responses that may show different values and habits, and this information will be used to form and recruit focus groups of balanced participants to co-create and discuss relevant research questions in the four fields of everyday life practice: energy at home, mobility, food, waste. Online citizens workshops can be organised with plenary sessions involving the whole group of 40 citizens and DIAMOND modellers, followed by breakout session for the four fields (approximately 10 citizens for each session), and again a plenary session to wrap up conclusions and recommendations. The detailed programming of such events will be decided and reported in the next issue of D2.1, at month 17.

4.2.3 Phase 3 – Towards model co-ownership

The detailed description of this phase will be provided in deliverable "D2.4-Quality, social robustness, practical relevance".

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